

Factors Affecting Awareness of Mental Health among Adults of Selected Area of Dehradun, Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Background:- Mental health awareness delivers a wide range of knowledge and encompasses recognition and help-seeking behaviour. Mental health services should be assess at ground level to monitor its delivery. Different mean of communication can use to highlight the mental health issues.

Objective:- To identify the factor affecting awareness of mental health among adults.

Materials and methods: Quantitative research approach with descriptive design was adapted for present study. Total 126 adults were selected through systematic random sampling. The tools administered consisted of baseline data, structured questionnaire on factor affecting awareness of mental health. Descriptive and inferential statistics used for analyses.

Result:-This study showed that the samples reported that majority of the factors affecting awareness of mental health was superstitious belief, history of mental illness, peer group.

Conclusion:-The study explored that majority of the factors responsible for mental illness was superstitious belief, history of mental illness, peer group.

KEYWORDS: Factors, awareness, mental health

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INTRODUCTION

The life cycle of the human being is a continuous process, which consists of a series of development in the human body. The modifications in the build develop with various stages of the life cycle. The adult is the stage of life at which an individual attains the physical and mental maturity.

Mental health awareness delivers a wide range of knowledge and encompasses recognition and help-seeking behaviour. A study conducted in Zambia (2010) revealed that stigma and discriminating to the mentally ill client is still present in the community.¹In a study in Tehran (2011) people reported that people suffering from mental illness are discriminated and not accepted in the community.²

In India, WHO reported that mental health problem has a high burden as, 2443 DALYs per 100,000 population. The suicide rate is 21.1 per 100,000 population. In Uttarakhand, the incidence rate of postpartum depression was 11% among mothers and the prevalence rate of depressive

disorder was 6% as per 2014 report. These belief and attitudes are a potential barrier to seeking optimal professional help.³

Material and Methods

The descriptive method was implemented with systematic sampling technique in the study. Study was done on all the adults of Bhogpur village of Doiwala block, Dehradun, Uttarakhand. Total samples was 126. The data was collected through structured factor affecting awareness of mental health questionnaire and demographic details was obtained through baseline data. The tools were structured questionnaire on factors affecting awareness of mental health contains 15 question with yes and no response. Administrative agreement was attained from Principal Himalayan College of Nursing, SRHU. The ethical permission was taken from the ethical committee of SRHU than written consent of the participants was taken before doing the collection of data.

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Table no.1 the table of percentage and frequency classification of factor affecting awareness of mental health in adults

S. No	Factor	Response	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
1.	Superstitious belief	Yes	110	87.3
2.	History of mental illness	Yes	105	83.3
3.	Peer group	Yes	104	82.5
4.	Family environment	Yes	103	81.7
5.	Long term physical illness	Yes	111	81.1
6.	Media and technology	Yes	102	81
7.	Financial status	Yes	100	79.4
8.	Low self-esteem and low - confidence	Yes	95	76.4
9.	Social issues and social instability	Yes	96	76.2
10.	Inaccessibility of mental health services	Yes	93	73.8
11.	Occupation and profession	Yes	86	68.3
12.	Physical disability	Yes	85	67.5
13.	Lower literacy rate	Yes	84	66.73
14.	Marriage	Yes	81	64.3
15.	Culture and religion	Yes	74	58.7

Table no.1 Showed that majority 87.3% samples reported that superstitious belief had effect on mental health, 83.3% of the samples were aware that history of mental illness was one of the factor that influence mental health, samples' responded related to peer group could affect the mental health i.e 82.5% and mental health in the community was influenced by family environment i.e 81.7%, long term physical illness was 81.1 % and 81% were media and technology. Some other factors like financial status 79.4%, low esteem and low self-confidence 76.4% and social issues and social instability 76.2% had effect on mental health.

DISCUSSION

The study aims to recognize the various factors affecting awareness of mental health A total of 126 samples were selected in the study, through the systematic random sampling techniques. The discussion was done according to objectives and with supportive study

Summary of findings

In the study samples the majority 30.15% of the adults stayed in the age set of 31- 40 years. 58.7% were females, 57.1 % were residing in the joint family. Maximum of the sample 33.3 % had secondary education. Family income of majority 69.84 % of the sample was between Rs 5000-10000. 65.07% were married, 95.2% followed the Hindu religion. Whole sample 100% had reported that they don't have any source of information regarding mental health and also don't have any past history of mental illness.

In the study it showed that various factors like superstitious belief, peer pressure, history of mental illness have influencing factor on awareness of mental health.

Factors affecting awareness of mental health among adults

The present study had acknowledged various factor affecting awareness of mental health in the community as

superstition, history of mental illness, peer group and family environment. Similar studies were also done on factors.

Chadda RK, Patra BN, Gupta N. (2013) reported that community mental health refers to the treatment of mental health disorders. According to many epidemiological studies of psychiatric disorder have been conducted in India on general population in the community. The prevalence rate varies from 9.5 to 370/1000 population. India is a culturally diverse country, explanations for mental disorders have been influenced by system of traditional medicine, supernatural beliefs, poor socioeconomic status of the people and limited awareness regarding mental illness in the community⁴

Gureje O, Lasebikan VO, Ephraim-Oluwanuga O, Olley BO, Kola L. (2005) conducted the study on knowledge and altered to mental illness. The purpose was to determine the community attitude and awareness. A multistage, clustered sample of household respondents was studied in three states in the Yoruba-speaking parts of Nigeria (representing 22% of the national population). Total 2040 individual included in the study. The study concluded that low knowledge is a concern in the community which leads to a negative view of mental illness. Stigmatization of mental illness was more prevalent in the Nigerian community.⁵

Strengths

The current study had the following strengths:

1. Sample size was calculated to determine the appropriate sampling technique.

Limitations

1. The opinion was on the basis of Yes and No which was limited to the area of response.
2. Small sample size limits the generalization of the result.

Conclusion

The study established that some factors like superstitious, history of mental illness, family environment, financial status, and peer group affect to mental health.

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